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Lean Leadership - Unlocking the Potential at the Bottom of the Pyramid

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Introduction:

In a world where global competition is absolute, organizations are noticing at new ways to gain sustained competitive advantages. The global financial crisis of 2008 and 2009 has overlapped with the earlier social tensions and anti-globalization movements in the twenty-first century. It is startling to observe that the least developed countries have become even worse off because of the global financial crisis (UNCTAD, 2008). This United Nations (UNCTAD, 2008) report also supports the theme of this article, to provide potential remedies and responses to such anti-globalizations movements, as globalization currently may not lead to equal distribution of the economic growth and wealth created. The global financial crisis helps us to further clarify the disproportionate and unequal economic effects that globalization inflicts onto the poorest countries in the world, also called, the bottom of pyramid (Hahn, 2009) countries. Responsible leadership (Pless et al., 2009) in the 21st century, requires a fairer, equal treatment of all managers, i.e. both expatriate and local managers within MNEs. The aim of this paper is therefore to contribute to a better understanding of lean leadership and BoP in the organizations. The primary research questions that were addressed in this study are as follows: What are the challenges of bottom of pyramid, and methods to manage organizations and develop employees? What are the characteristics of Lean leadership, including role, style and behaviors of Lean leaders? How is local managers connected with BoP?

Bottom of Pyramid (BoP) and Challenges:

Several companies have derived BoP strategies from C.K. Prahalad, the excellent management guru. Marketing theories from the 4Ps to the 5Cs have failed when trying to involve the BoP. Instead, Prahalad presents a new framework, the 4 As – Awareness, Access, Affordability and Availability. *Awareness* confirms customers and suppliers in the BOP know the product / service exists, *Access* confirms consumers have access to the products whether it's the slums of city. *Affordability* is dominant and most innovation challenges lie in this space and lastly *Availability* builds trust and loyalty with the BoP masses by ensuring a steady supply of products and services. There are certain excellent business & corporate strategy examples of companies implementing the BoP model. One enterprise is the global conglomerate LG and the other is a social enterprise start-up based out of India called Sevamob. Sevamob offers healthcare and advisory solutions to the BoP masses in the North India. The business model is contribution based & very inexpensive around \$2 / month. The services are provided through agents with wireless tablets who travel to far-off regions in mobile vans. They provide guidance on the spot and can generate "trouble tickets" which are then handled by subject matter experts through a network, coordinated by a 24/7 call center. Mobile agents (insurers, doctors, agriculture experts) carry these handheld devices to relay advice and look back upon previous engagements in order to craft custom solutions. Furthermore, the agents communicate the villagers' languages and eliminate obstacles such as illiteracy and absences of data networks.

Sevamob is growing by leaps and bounds and touches upon all facets of Prahalad's model – *Awareness* (generated by traveling agents & word of mouth), *Access* (mobile vans & wireless tablets provide access to solutions), *Affordability* (\$2/month) and lastly *Availability* – villagers have come to trust the timely services from Sevamob. Investing in developing markets naturally represents certain challenges. Largest challenges for companies entering BoP market is very limited purchasing power of individual consumer. The organization must think in the different way to reap benefits of these markets. If the price of innovative product is set outside the range of potential customer the product fails in the market. Limited product awareness and lack of understanding are also the hurdles of bottom of pyramid.

Lean:

“LEAN IS... an attitude or way of thinking, with a dedication to attain a totally waste-free operation that's alert on the customer's success. It is accomplished by making simpler and continuously improving all processes and relationships in an environment of trust, respect and complete employee involvement. It is about people, flow, visibility, partnerships, simplicity and true value as perceived by the customer.” “Work smarter, not harder” is the fundamental theme of organizations that have successfully implemented a Lean performance management framework as they demonstrate workflow processes that are simple and meaningful, eliminate waste and improve productivity and customer satisfaction. The end outcome is a cultural transformation that aligns strategy, culture, and accomplish that can improve internal and external communications, reduce employee stress, increase customer satisfaction, and offer overall cost savings to an organization.

Lean Leadership:

The term “leadership” can be conceptualized in different ways. Though, according to Northouse (1997) some common themes that are central to the phenomenon of leadership can be identified. These themes are: leadership is a process; leadership involves goal attainment and influence; leadership occurs within a group context, (Northouse, 1997). The authors however see many similarities with contemporary leadership theories such as transformational leadership, servant leadership and leadership in self-managed teams. Hence these theories will be briefly presented in this section.

The servant leadership theory was developed by Greenleaf in the 1970s and is based on the idea that a leader is a servant. The main objective of servant leaders is to help and meet the needs of others, which should be essential motivation for leadership (Greenleaf and Spears, 2002). Servant leadership is associated to transformational leadership and there is a debate as to whether there are any differences between these two theories (Stone et al., 2004). Transformational leadership and servant leadership emphasize the consideration and appreciation of individuals, the importance of teaching, coaching, developing, and empowering followers (Stone et al., 2004). There is a growing trend in organisations to give more responsibility for daily activities to teams rather than individuals (Yukl, 1997). Teams with a multi-skilled workforce are the fundamental work unit in Lean organisations (Liker, 2004) and the principles behind the teamwork have a strong connection to the concept of self-managed teams. In self-managed teams there are two types of leaders: internal leaders who coordinate team activities, and external leaders who support the team's self-management (Yukl, 1997). According to Mann (2005), a Lean management system entails of four prime elements: visual controls, daily accountability processes, leader standard work, and discipline. Liker and Convis (2011) present a leadership model describing the most vital characteristics of Toyota leadership. The model entails of four stages: 1. Commit to Self-Development; 2. Coach & Develop Others; 3. Support Daily Kaizen 4. Create Vision & Align Goals. Lean leadership needs to be supported by Lean managerial practices and tools (Liker and Convis, 2011).

Figure 1: The Inverted Pyramid in Lean Leadership

The leader's job at Toyota is First, acquire each person to take initiative to solve problems and improve his or her job. Second, confirm that each person's job is aligned to provide value for the customer and fortune for the company. Old "Autocrat" leadership style is "Do it my way...". In the 1980s "Empowerment" leadership style is "Do it your way... "but, Lean leadership style is "Follow me... and let's figure this out together". : Serving leaders turn over the pyramid of conventional management thinking. They put themselves at the BoP and unleash the energy, excitement and skills of the team, business and community. All are identical, all are called to lead, all are mentors.

Essential Qualities of a Lean Leadership:

During the past decade, many multinationals have come up short trying to make a profit by solving the pressing needs of low-income communities. Organizations are violently managing costs these days. As a result, it's gloomy to see even some affirmed lean leaders turning away from the principles and qualities that make them not merely exceptional leaders but lean ones. Possibly it's time to analyze some of the essential qualities of a lean leader that end in profits.

Perspective:

The lean leader should hold a long-term perspective and guide their organization to make decisions that are in their best interests over the long haul. The depth of perception requires the leader to be curious enough to go see, pay attention, connect with people and study about the work in detail. A lean leader sees beyond their own horizon, is conscious of the larger impact of actions and perceives in terms of total costs.

Responsibility:

Lean leaders need the quality of strong responsibility, social responsibility, in order to earn lasting results and respect. Further, an organization needs to have a good understanding of their potential BoP customers before designing products and distribution channels.

Openness:

Leaders must be open to change. Taiichi Ohno said that half of the time even sages are wrong. Most leaders are no sages, and need to be open to being wrong so they can correct their ways.

Flexibility:

A lean leader must be able to quickly adjust to differences in styles and to be a skilled two-way communicator. Flexibility for a lean leader is the talent to accommodate differences in style.

communication, and context without reverting to type and defining the problem as it fits their favored personal solution

Teamwork:

Competent lean leader must be willing to identify, influence and be influenced by the needs of their team. A lean leader effectively links one's own goals with the goals of the group, removes obstacles to enable teamwork, and finds strongly with the team but does not crowd it.

Self-knowledge:

To effectively lead the team and to take control of the organization and, leader needs to get control of her first. True self-knowledge should lead to humility. The ability to reflect and do hansei (self-reflection), constantly learn, and to give and accept challenges is the mark of a true lean leader. A person who possesses and is guided by these essential qualities will guide their people towards profits.

Local managers and local knowledge:

Knowledge is increasingly perceived as the key competitive advantage of today's MNEs (Foss, 2007). Gaining of local knowledge requires formal and informal structures in as well as responsible leadership (Pless et al., 2009) to allow fair and equal social interactions, working closely with local associations. Responsible leadership (Pless et al., 2009) in the 21st century will need such shared, social identities within the MNE. Cohesion of any social group requires shared social identity and worldview (Coleman, 1990). This identity should be rooted in shared and tacit beliefs. Trust is important to social cohesion that groups are not interested in mortgaging their existing cohesion to some singular set of definable explicit criteria alone. This duality exists for expatriate & local managers alliances in MNEs, where the value of local managers should be perceived in knowledge and institutional as well as market value (North, 1990) terms. This dual approach is illustrated in Figure 2. There is no question that in certain circumstances, and for specific determinations, using expatriate rather than local managers can have benefits, especially in enabling a corporation to keep control over foreign subsidiaries (McGuire and Hutchings, 2006). However, the substitute approach can also be valid as there is a rising appreciation that the strengths which local Responsible Leadership for Multinational Enterprises in Bottom of Pyramid Countries managers bring to their managerial roles for instance in, bottom of pyramid countries (Haha, 2009) many research has quoted recent moves of Japanese firms to reduce their reliance on expatriates reflects the understanding by Japanese firms of this phenomenon. The reasons, though changing in specific cases, point in the similar direction: local managers can understand better and interact effectively with the local community in which the firm is operating. Local managers are able to reduce uncertainties and develop suitable strategies and tactics for the local labour and market conditions. There are two issues: an alienation of local managers and when they are present, the isolation or exclusion of these local managers. Not permitting local managers, this greater role and participation through the local community makes a social isolation for the local managers in the circumstance of the global knowledge-based organisation (Spendier et al., 2007). Empowering lean leadership will help MNE to attain global competitiveness through the effective leveraging of local manager's knowledge.

Figure 2. Local managers in bottom of pyramid countries – market, community and institutional knowledge.

Source: Ron Berger et al.,(2011)

Conclusion:

The global financial crisis of 2008 and 2009 has raised social tensions all over the world and generates greater contests for, responsible leadership. “Bottom of Pyramid” (BOP) has emphasized that marketing to the world’s poor is a profitable endeavor for multinational companies. This article contested that MNEs has to follow lean leadership and need to assess local managers’ knowledge and contributions not only for operational and market value, but also organizational value, such as access to local knowledge and local social capital. The extreme price sensitivity of BoP consumer requires dramatic cost reduction to create product and services that these consumers are affordable. Innovative product and value chain are foremost for success at BoP. Innovation, cost reduction and value chain can be accomplished through lean practices and lean leadership.

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